

**LANGUAGE AND GOVERNANCE: A PRAGMATIC STUDY OF ACHEBE'S
*ANTHILLS OF THE SAVANNAH***

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Abstract

This study examines language use in governance and its implication for positive nationhood in Achebe's *Anthills of the Savannah*. In Nigeria and Africa, many leaders use language devoid of politeness considerations and this situation has caused various shades of clashes that hinder positive nationhood. Consequently, the face-threatening acts and violations of politeness maxims in a leader's language use in the text are assessed. The strategies for face-threatening act are highlighted. Forty excerpts selected from the study text serve as data for examining the variables identified. Goffman's (1967) Face-act theory, Leech's (1973) Politeness Maxims and Austin's (1972) Speech Act theories constitute the theoretical approaches for data analysis. From the investigation, it is discovered that utterances of a leader devoid of politeness and face considerations are harbingers of conflict. It is recommended that such matters as language use in administration should not be neglected.